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ANTAGONISM BETWEEN FLIES AND BEES

Antagonismo tra mosche e api

Honey bees, bumblebees, leafcutter bees and mason bees can all be managed for pollination purposes. Honeybees for pollination of crops, bumblebees for plants cultivated in greenhouses, leafcutter bees for alfalfa and mason bees for orchards. To manage honeybees and bumblebees humans trade on eusociality while for leafcutter bees and mason bees on their gregarious nesting (BOHART 1962; ASENSIO 1982; BOSCH *et al.*, 1994; KRUNIC *et al.* 1995; SPLITT *et al.*, 2022). The immediate consequence of managing these bees is an increase in the number of apiaries, hives and bee hotels in areas where unmanaged bees could also be present. High concentration of managed bees favours the spill over and spread of pathogens as well as the increase of predators, parasites, parasitoids and nest destroyers that are threats for unmanaged populations of these and other wild bees. In this scenario the antagonism of four bees and three of their parasitoid flies is here described. The bees are: the superorganism *Apis mellifera*, the eusocial *Bombus terrestris* and the two solitary bees *Megachile rotundata* and *Osmia cornuta*. The flies are two endoparasitoids, *Senotainia tricuspis* (FELICOLI, 2014) and *Physocephala vittata* (FREEMAN, 1966), and one ectoparasitoid, *Anthrax anthrax* (KRUNIC *et al.*, 1995).

The larviparous sarcophagid *S. tricuspis* is able to detect honeybee hives and to exploit their roofs as a base to ambush flying foragers and follow them during their flight and, within a sixth of a second, laying a single larva on the bee thorax (HADDAD *et al.*, 1015). Conversely the conopid

P. vittata uses flowers as base to ambush both bumblebees and leafcutter bees during their foraging activity, it then clamps a single egg on the host *gastrum* intermembrane. The bombyliid *A. anthrax* is strongly attracted by the pedothropic nests of the mason bees. They fill up their sand chamber with some fine dust to separate each sticky egg and then hover in front of the bee nest to perform its egg casting behaviour shooting a single sticky egg at the bee nest entrance.

The *S. tricuspis* first instar larvae is able to penetrate the bee thorax through cuticle, or possibly through the thoracic bee tracheal spiracles, and feed on the bee thoracic muscles weakening the forager until causing an early death. Also the *P. vittata* larva enters the body of both bumblebee and leafcutter bee but through the abdomen instead of the thorax. After the third instar larva is reached, the bumblebee will die away from the colony and such adaptive suicide (SMITH TRAIL, 1980; FRITZ, 1982) has had two different interpretations: as a host advantage (SCHMID-HEMPEL *et al.*, 1991; MULLER *et al.*, 1992) or a parasitoid advantage (POULIN, 1992). Leafcutter bees die either inside or next to the nest. In this case the same parasitoid induce a behaviour that differs in the two host species, indicating that maybe the host behaviour is not linked to some evolutionary advantage of the host or of the parasite but is more probably the consequence of the damage of different body structures. From the *A. anthrax* egg stuck at the entrance of the mason bee nest, a tiny larva called *planidium* will hatch. Before the bee cocoon is spun, the *planidium* reaches the mason bee larva moving by its two mouth hooks, and by special structures present in its thorax and in the abdomen. The *planidium* reaches the mason bee larva using its two mouth hooks, six thorax and two caudal appendices before the bee cocoon is spun. Just after the cocoon is spun the *planidium* starts to feed and the more the *A. anthrax* larva is growing the more the bee larva collapses.

The *S. tricuspis* third instar larva emerges from the dead forager neck, feeds further on the dead bee then digs into the ground and pupate. Depending on latitude the endoparasitoid *S. tricuspis* shows a monovoltin or bivoltin cycle. The *P. vittata* third instar larva pupate inside the host abdomen. Like a matryoshka the bee abdomen contains the fly *puparium* which, in turns, contains the fly pupa. After the metamorphosis the fly imago, by use of a special head transitory structure called *ptilinum* opens both its puparium and the bee *gastrum*. Within the same cohort of age some pupae will overwinter and some will emerge later in the season. The *P. vittata* is a parsivoltin fly. The *A. anthrax* grown larva pupates inside the bee cocoon, the pupa is called armed pupa due to its six-cefalic spurs and three sharp points in the caudal region. The armed

pupa oscillating and rotating is able to cut the cocoon and to move towards the edge of the bee nest, crushing all the bee cocoons that are inside the nest. In this stage the *A. anthrax* pupa is also a nest destroyer (FABRE, 1915; KRUNIC *et al.*, 1995). Also the ectoparasitoid *A. anthrax* shows a parsivoltin cycle (DU MERLE, 1972).

If seventy per cent of foragers is parasitized by *S. tricuspis* fly, the entire honeybee colony will die. The Conopid fly *P. vittata* parasitize the parental generation of bumblebees and leafcutter bees that will reduce their egg laying affecting the next generation up to forty per cent. The bombyliid fly *A. anthrax* can reduce the host population up to ninety per cent due to direct parasitization and cocoons crushing (FELICOLI *et al.*, 2017).

Bad management of these four bees could be a threat for wild unmanaged local bees whereas good management could be a tool to mitigate the impact of those interspecific antagonism.

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